

THEORETICAL BACKGROUNDS OF TRADITIONAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS

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Abstract: *Global expansion and qualitative change of international bilateral contacts and relations in all areas and Uzbekistan’s transformation into an open society, intensive looking in learning foreign languages has argueded significantly in recent decades in the country. It becomes a crucial factor of scientific, technical, general cultural progress, especially economy in our modern society. All of which contributes to raising the foreign language status as a main skill to be developed in all spheres. Nowadays, students are experiencing new technological inventions and are applying for their own life and educational process therefore when they are having lessons with traditional methods they may be bored and no interest for the lesson. Additionally, they are having the vast majority of videos on You Tube, Facebook, Instagram and other social media; as a result they are getting disappointed by having traditional lessons with traditional methods. In Uzbekistan, many teachers are keen on using technological methods in EFL classrooms; therefore, many researches have been investigating and conducted among young learners and linguistics. The main aim of it to prove scientifically, practically, technological methods may overweigh traditional methods.*

Key words: *technology, EFL classrooms, methods, traditional methods, technology based methods, social Media*

Introduction. Traditional education lasted 600 centuries, starting from the Middle Ages. By the twenty-first century, this permanent traditional method of teaching had failed. Some estimates of the effectiveness of higher education are measured based on the growth in the number of students entering universities around the world. Traditional teaching strategies are a group of strategies that were used in the past that are now considered to be largely outdated. These strategies were the primary teaching methods employed in the early days of the modern education system (circa 1800 -1930s) when teachers were not required to undertake any form of teacher training.

Technology is a powerful tool that has a positive impact on learning. By showing students how to use it effectively, teachers can eliminate several negative associations to create a safe and effective learning environment. As a result, students will be more involved and motivated to work on interesting and interactive learning tasks. They also develop the skills necessary for success in the future. Computer technology is a positive addition to bridging the gap between education and the technological world in which we live. Although effective training is possible, different technologies are combined. Computer technologies in schools offer students access to information, motivation to learn, a quick start of sales of work skills and improving the quality of work in the classroom.

Methodology.

In this research, qualitative and quantitative methods were used. In order to compare to two different types of methods, comparative method was used to gather information. In order to find information, different articles and books on the Internet were analyzed and concluded.

Results and discussion.

Technology seems to be gradually taking over many aspects of human society. Education has gradually evolved to incorporate technology into the dissemination of information. This progress has revolutionized the learning environment, resulting in improved grades and learning experiences. Although a small group of conservative-minded people are skeptical about using technology in the classroom, the benefits are obvious. Now the question remains, how best to use technology in the classroom and what are the potential benefits? As tablet computers and other smart devices gradually replace textbooks, we also need to study the challenges faced by the introduction of technology in education. The main argument in favor of introducing technology into the classroom is that students should easily apply classroom concepts in everyday life. Understanding the role of technology in classrooms and the workplace, among other things, is crucial. Before focusing on the pros and cons of technology based classrooms, the types of technologies should be introduced. The following types of technologies have already played an important role in technology based classrooms.

1. Using computers in the classroom: - computers have evolved and changed their appearance and way of working. Now desktop computers and laptop computers, also often known as laptops or notebooks. New technologies have also emerged, and some new computers, such as the iPod or galaxy Tablet, have a skilful birth. These computers can be used by teachers to assign work to students and study groups in the classroom. Teachers can also use computers to illustrate visual themes that help students learn

more easily. Modern computers come with built-in applications that help students learn better.

2. Creating websites and blogs in the classroom: - Creating a website or blog using Word Click or other content management software is very simple. Teachers can create cool blogs if they post assignments. If the school does not have a website switch to host these cool blogs, the teacher can use free website hosting services such as Word click. through these platforms, the teacher creates a blog under the subdomain of this host. Students will find all their study assignments in this blog.

3. Using mobile devices:-teachers and students can use smartphones in the classroom for academic purposes. Mobile learning is becoming very popular. This is similar to e-learning or distance learning. Although it is based on mobile phones. It's good from the spot because M-Learning is convenient. Mobile phones are very light, but they can have the same software as on a regular computer, a student can receive academic information, such as assignments, through an educational mobile application.

4.Using intelligent interactive whiteboards: - Modern intelligent whiteboards have a touch screen function, so the teacher can depict dots using a projector, teachers can display visual effects on these whiteboards, which improves the learning process. Students learn more easily through visual effects. Students can also use the whiteboard to draw, write, or manipulate images. Smart boards come in different sizes, wider ones are better because they can display a larger image and can be used by two students at the same time.

5. Using digital microphones in the classroom: - large classrooms are characterized by unlimited noise levels, so teachers can use these wireless digital microphones. The microphone transmits the sound to the speakers, and each student clearly hears his teacher. This helps the teacher not to strain his voice trying to explain thoughts to his students. These digital microphones are not very expensive, so even a school with a small income can afford to buy a wireless microphone for each class.

6.Using Online Media: - Teachers and students can use online streaming tools to teach in the classroom. Using a projector, a computer, the internet and a blackboard, the teacher shows an example in real time using the following sites: youtube.com.there are videos on this website that can be used for academic information. As far as technology has very important role in teaching, there are lots of advantages of technology in the classrooms.

1. Technology gives opportunity for students to be aware of the most current information available. Electronic textbooks or web based content can be updated in real-time all around world. Classrooms can connect with other classrooms without any problems around the world to broaden their learning and to expand their outlook and

mindset. This benefit of technology can cause the wide opportunity door to connect with the world and share their knowledge.

2. Students are able to practice collaboration skills by working in teams on projects utilizing shared documents or conferencing technologies. This allows collaboration to occur outside of the classroom or among classrooms in different locations. This means that they can connect with different people in any time and any place that they want.

It is true that the collaboration with people costs money, time, energy without technology, because they need to spend their time and money to get one destination. Therefore, the technology can help students and teachers to collaborate in an easy way.

3. It is without question that students will need to know how to use technology to communicate and collaborate in their future careers. If students want to get well-paid job in their future career, they have to know how to use technology. When technology is used in the classroom, they have to use it.

4. Effective teaching methods - to enrich the education system, it is very important to ensure effective implementation of teaching methods for teachers and professors. When it is looked specifically at teachers' perceptions, the vast majority of empirical findings indicate that EFL teachers have positive perceptions of technology use in the classroom (Aydin 2013; Canals and Al-Rawashdeh 2019; Huang et al. 2019; Morgana and Shrestha 2018; O'Bryan and Hegelehimer 2007; Thang et al. 2014) Because these contribute greatly to the improvement of students' knowledge (Isisag (2012)). Before the advent of technology, teachers primarily used textbooks and explained concepts on the board. But with the advent of technology, they are gaining in-depth knowledge and ensuring understanding of concepts among students. Apart from explaining the concepts to the students, they can also show them pictures and images so that they can have a better understanding (Ding et al. 2019). The use of technology allows teachers to adequately implement teaching methods. Whereas students are able to implement effective methods of understanding and learning.

5. Improving Independent Work - Despite the use of technology, improvements are being made in students' independent work competencies. Students, especially those who are slow to grasp concepts or have learning disabilities, tend to depend on others. When teachers teach and depend on classmates, friends, or family members, they are unable to grasp concepts effectively. Thus, when they learn to use information technology, they can expand their understanding in terms of concepts. With a proper understanding of the topics and concepts, they are able to overcome various obstacles and difficulties associated with the implementation of tasks. Therefore, when they need

to work on a project or assignment, they are able to work independently with minimal or no help from others.

6. Activation of the educational system - the use of information technologies makes a great contribution to the activation of the educational system. There are many aspects that are affected by the use of information technology in the educational system (Siefert et al. 2019),. These include teaching methods, teaching strategies, interactive learning, individualized and differentiated approach to teaching, cognitive activity and self-control among students through the use of video and audio information. includes testing and control through a system of equations. In some cases, sufficient understanding of the concepts is provided by videos when teachers are teaching lesson plans or when students are presenting their research projects in higher education institutions. One of the most important aspects is that students can make improvements in knowledge and information acquisition. As a result, they could improve their academic performance and achieve their academic goals.

7. Taking Online Courses - Individuals are pursuing bachelor's, master's, or doctoral programs at institutions of higher education. They even have to take online courses while doing these programs. Online classes are more common in other countries like the United States of America than in Uzbekistan. One of the main limitations of online classes is that people do not have the opportunity to listen to class lectures or to establish appropriate conditions and relationships with other individuals. To pursue online courses, they must first access the internet. If people are located far away, in other regions or countries, they use the internet to do online courses. Moreover, the websites such as Coursera or British council website announce free courses every year.

8. Online Education - Online education provides opportunities to use multimedia tools in the learning process. This includes the use of color, animation, sound and video. School teachers and professors of colleges and universities have the opportunity to use in terms of visibility of the materials used to improve teaching methods, teaching strategies and improve the overall system of education. By providing online education, individuals who cannot attend classroom lectures or live far away can continue their courses and programs(Korkut, 2012).

Disadvantages of technology in the classroom

As far as the coin has two sides, the technology based classroom has drawbacks too. It is proved that the technology in the classroom can give tons of opportunities for not only teachers but also students and pupils when they are used in effective way. Otherwise, they will be dangerous and distracting. Therefore, there are several disadvantages of technology as follows:

1. As far as the lesson is conducted by the help of the different gadgets, students are constantly in front of a device — cell phones, tablets, computers, and gaming devices which are prevalent in their lives. Lucy Kidwell (25, 2022) says that “ A Healthy Minds Network 2020 survey divulged that two-thirds of college students struggled with loneliness, with a whopping 83 percent indicating that poor mental health detracted from their academic performance. This is notable, as these higher instances of depression and anxiety—as well as tense relationships, eye strain, poor sleep, and physical health complications—are directly tied to excessive screen time.” Adding technology to the classroom increases the overall amount of exposure to electronic devices and screen time, as a result, students may forget spend outdoors. On the top of that there are concerns that too much screen time can easily damage eyesight. When they spend their time working with devices they may get depressed and feel alone. As a result, they feel lonely and this may lead some physiological disorders. This influence can be minimized if parents and teachers can control the number of hours students spend in front of screens.

2. Technology not only help to teach but also it can help to distract students attention as far as technology can be a minefield of distractions. Ads, pop-ups, games, news, interesting websites, social media, instant text messages, and so on and so forth are constantly competing for our attention. Moreover, students use their smartphones and tablets, naturally there may be social media and they may get distracted by instant messages. This means teachers have tendency to face the challenge of keeping students concentrated on their task. It is stated in a study published in the Journal of Educational Psychology that 118 upper-level college students were interviewed, it is proven that the students with laptops, tablets and smart phones open for non-classroom purposes scored half a letter grade lower on exams. In order to solve this problem, teachers can assist encourage students to focus on their work by setting clear expectations and consequences. Additionally, teachers at classrooms and parents at home can also set up internet blocks on Google, Facebook and other social medias to help keep students from visiting other sites when they are supposed to be working.

Learning styles have evolved significantly over the years. While the traditional method of teaching is carried out with the help of reading and memorization techniques, the modern style of work includes interactive methods.

The traditional teaching method, also known as traditional teaching, is still widely used in schools. The old style of teaching was associated with reading, for example, the students sat in silence, and one by one the students took turns reading the lesson until each of them was called. The teacher listened to each student’s reading, and they

had to learn and memorize the assignments. At the end of the module, a written test or an oral exam is conducted; this process consists of studying a task called a reading test.

The method of teaching traditional methods ensured that students would be rewarded for their efforts, use lesson cycles effectively, and use clear rules to manage student behavior. They were based on established traditions that have been successfully used in schools for many years. Teachers passed on knowledge and standards of behavior. There are lots of advantages and disadvantages of traditional teaching in classroom. The advantages of traditional teaching are as follows:

Less Distraction

Technology-based methods are designed to be fast, easy and convenient, but are they applicable in practice? For many employees, e-learning is something that fits into their working day, but what happens when training is interrupted by a call or a small talk with a colleague? People are easily distracted by e-learning. According to a study published in the journal of the Educational Technology Association (Alt), a number of students they interviewed reported that the unexplored applications of the technologies they used distracted them from learning. Traditional classroom activities are designed to allow students to participate in the curriculum with minimal distractions. This type of teaching forces students to focus on their focus and focus on the subject on the side without distracting them from email and colleagues.

Human Elements

The human factor also plays a role in the assimilation of educational material. "In addition, the role of emotions in adult education is very important because they are closely related to meaning and cognitive construction" (Dirkx, 2001; Shuck et al., 2007). Understanding that adult learners use their senses to gain and retain information and knowledge is important for the learning experience.

If a student goes through technology-based learning, they may have some shortcomings in human behavior that are related to learning emotions. For example, on a standard online video course, there may be no sound tone produced and, of course, transmitted by the message of the material. When taking classes in the classroom, the student has instructions from the coach that he can use to try to remember the information later.

As it is said that the coin has two sides, traditional teaching has disadvantages as follows:

Lacks Student Focused Learning

The disadvantage of traditional education is that it attaches the greatest importance to standards, curricula and passing tests, as opposed to student-centered learning. Student-centered learning attaches importance to the student and structures

the curriculum around questions that young people must answer in order to understand the material. Constructivist education is based on the knowledge that students already have, which allows them to create clear associations with new information, which improves memorization. Traditional education is based on repetition and memorization of facts that care less about students and maintain low grades after the test.

Lacks Emphasis on Critical Thinking

Traditional classroom activities do not encourage critical thinking skills, the ability to actively apply information obtained as a result of experiments and reasoning. Instead, traditional classes emphasize the role of teachers as distributors of knowledge and students as repositories. This learning style does not provide students with a deeper understanding of the complex concepts and knowledge needed for lifelong learning. Students who have completed traditional training must take a test with an emphasis, for test materials or not. Thus, the learning process is devalued, and students are not encouraged to understand the methods, techniques and skills needed to find answers. Constructivist education makes the process as important as the results, because it encourages skills and abilities are important long after school.

Neglect of larger concepts or structures

Instead of focusing on larger concepts and treating the context of learners in learning as constructivist learning, traditional learning focuses on key skills and gradually builds into a cohesive whole. While this simplifies learning, it provides a little context that can alienate students.

Lacks Interactivity

Traditional classes focus on individual work and projects of students and are poorly prepared for the future work of students, which includes teamwork and collaboration with colleagues. According to this learning model, students have few opportunities to participate in group dynamics and teamwork.

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